

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC ON THE EXCHANGE RATE OF THE RUSSIAN NATIONAL CURRENCY

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Abstract

This article considers the impact of the coronavirus pandemic on the ruble exchange rate. In modern realities, the exchange rate, having a strong relationship with the main macroeconomic indicators, has a tangible impact on the country's economic system. The ruble exchange rate was analyzed using multiple linear regression (MLR) correlation analysis. The results have shown that the price of oil significantly affects the exchange rate. Moreover, other independent variables such as RTS Index and foreign investment in Federal loan bonds included in the model also have a distinguished effect on the ruble exchange rate.

Keywords: Exchange rate, Brent oil price, RTS index, Federal loan bonds

I. INTRODUCTION

On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization announced the start of a pandemic of a new coronavirus infection of COVID-19, which has affected all countries of the world.

The pandemic has caused the largest global recession in 80 years, which was accompanied by large-scale isolation of the population. Global stock markets finally collapsed in March 2020, when major global indices fell by several percent. The general director of the World Health Organization, Tedros Ghebreyesus, expressed the hope that the coronavirus pandemic would be overcome in less than two years, therefore, by 2021 it will not be possible to finally "defeat" the coronavirus infection. In this regard, a wide range of opinions are expressed on the future dynamics of the ruble exchange rate, but the situation continues to be uncertain, since the pandemic process itself has so far indefinite characteristics, which is reflected in an increase in the degree of uncertainty of all economic and social processes. [1] The exchange rate is one of the most important macro-parameters of the open economy, therefore, the study of the actual dynamics of the ruble exchange rate and the identification of factors is affecting it in the specific conditions of the global pandemic remains highly relevant. [2]

The pandemic of coronavirus infection has significantly shaken the Russian economy. Since the beginning of 2020, the ruble's exchange rate against the dollar has grown by 16.52 rubles from 61.91 to 78.43 rubles [3] and almost reached a historical maximum in the history of the Russian Federation, including the event of 2014, called "Black Tuesday," when the ruble's exchange rate against the dollar in one day soared from 61 to 80 rubles. During the analyzed period, the price of oil also fell significantly: by \$38.93 per barrel from 58.16 to \$19.23.

In this research it will be determine the degree of influence of factors such as RTS Index, volume of Federal loan bonds owned by non-residents (in billion rubles); and oil prices Brent (the price is indicated in US dollars per barrel) on the exchange rate of the US dollar pair in Russian rubles.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The theory of exchange rate is a theoretical model of the determination and change of foreign price exchange rate of currency, also known as the theory of exchange rate determination. The central idea is that the exchange rate is determined by the supply and demand of foreign exchange. Western exchange rate theories are complicated and various schools, including traditional exchange rate theories and modern exchange rate theories. Some demonstrating exchange rate determination, and others explaining exchange rate changes. As a part of financial theory, exchange rate theory has developed from a subsidiary theory to an independent theory along with the process of exchange rate system from simple to complex. As the core topic of international financial theory research, exchange rate theory is an important part of international economic system. Its development runs through the whole history of modern western economic thought. It has always been a hot issue in western international economic research, and new theories emerge in endlessly. Exchange rate theory mainly includes the following two aspects: one is the determination of exchange rate. Under the floating exchange rate system, the volatile exchange rate not only affects the interests of micro subjects, but also relates to the internal and external balance of the national economy. The determination of exchange rate and the factors influencing the exchange rate change have become the hot issues of international financial scholars; the second is the exchange rate system. [4]

Consider factors that affect the exchange rate of the Russian national currency in modern realities. The factors affecting the ruble exchange rate can be divided into two main groups: internal and external factors. Internal factors of currency exchange rate formation include:

- 1) The Central Bank's key rate;
- 2) Unemployment rate;
- 3) Inflation rate;
- 4) RTS Index;
- 5) Federal loan bonds;
- 6) Balance of payments;
- 7) GNP of the country and industrial production index, etc. [2]

External factors affecting the ruble exchange rate include:

1) Oil prices. The profitable part of the country for more than half consists of profits provided by the export of raw materials, including oil. The prices of the raw materials from that make up Russian exports also have an impact.

2) The situation in the world economy. During the process of globalization, countries became interdependent, so news and changes in the world influence the national currency and the country directly.

3) Current sanctions. It did not stop working at a difficult time for the world economy.

4) Closing boundaries. The economy and industry are interethnic and interregional. [5]

However, in addition to these, there are many others factors affecting the growth of the ruble exchange rate.

The concept of the exchange rate is inseparable from the concept of the foreign exchange market. The currency market can be described as a certain centralized platform on which currency transactions are carried out, which are based on the fluctuation in the demand and supply of foreign currency for sale to the national currency and the subsequent formation of the exchange rate. The combination of world, national and regional markets, which differ in the volume, nature of foreign exchange transactions, as well as the list of currencies that are available for operations form a single global foreign exchange market. [6]

For the period of 2020, one can argue about the great dependence of the economic situation in the country on the foreign exchange market and, in particular, on the ruble exchange rate. The pandemic of coronavirus once again showed the dependence of the Russian economy on the fall in oil prices.

The difficult negotiations on the OPEC + deal, designed to reduce oil production, and for the Russian Federation to strengthen the ruble exchange rate and stabilize oil prices, at the moment do not provide a complete understanding for long-term planning of foreign exchange policy and the overall economic situation. [7]

Fig. 1. Russia's oil production, million tonnes

From Fig. 1. it can be seen, Oil production in Russia in 2021. fell to a low of 343.4 million tons in the last ten years. [8]

The shock of the pandemic was exacerbated in March 2020 by a sharp drop in oil prices, as shown in figure 2, and the associated instability in financial markets.

Fig. 2. Brent oil price dynamics, USD

The cost of a barrel of Brent crude oil is one of the main brands of oil traded on international oil exchanges, mainly on ICE (IntercontinentalExchange) [9].

The RTS index is a price, market capitalization-weighted composite index of the Russian stock market, which includes the most liquid shares of the largest and dynamically developing Russian issuers, whose economic activities belong to the main sectors of the economy. This index reflects the economic situation of the country. Accordingly, the RTS index either affects or is related to the exchange rate of the US dollar in rubles. [10]

Federal loan bonds are government debt obligations issued by the Ministry of Finance of Russia, denominated either in rubles or in foreign currency to attract funds, including non-residents of the Russian Federation.

In Russia, the share of demand for government securities in recent years is presented by non-residents, whose share in the domestic government market Russia's debt is high. Foreign investors are attracted by the high yield of federal loan bonds, which has a small chance of falling due to high rate of the Bank of Russia.

Given the fact that in Russia there are no restrictions on the movement of capital, such investors, with a decrease in the profitability of Federal loan bonds or an unnecessary change in the exchange rate of the ruble against the US dollar, foreign investors can withdraw invested funds from the market at any time. This can happen, for example, due to the introduction of additional packages sanctions that will impose restrictions on the purchase of Federal loan bonds by non-

residents or other shocks of the foreign exchange market. Which will ultimately negatively affect the ruble exchange rate. [7]

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It will be analyzed the ruble exchange rate using multiple linear regression (MLR) correlation analysis.

MLR allows to answer questions that consider the role(s) that multiple independent variables play in accounting for variance in a single dependent variable.

The formula for a multiple linear regression is:

$$Y_i = a + b_1X_{1i} + b_2X_{2i} + \dots + b_kX_{ki} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where, for $i=n$ observations:

Y_i - the predicted value of the dependent variable

a - a point estimate of free term

X_{1i}, X_{2i}, X_{ki} - independent variable

b_1, b_2, b_k - the regression coefficient (the effect that increasing the value of the independent variable has on the predicted Y_i value)

ε_i - the model's error term [11]

With the help of it, it will be established the degree of influence of such factors as the RTS Index, the volume of Federal loan bonds owned by non-residents (in billion rubles); and Brent oil prices (price indicated in United States dollars per barrel) on the exchange rate of the US dollar pair in Russian rubles. This study used exchanged rate as main dependent variable.

The data are taken by average monthly values, except for foreign investments in Federal loan bonds, the value of which is indicated on the first day of the reporting month. Used data from the resource Investing.com[12], the website of the Moscow Exchange [13], the website of the Central Bank of Russia [14].

Table 1. Baseline Data For Average Monthly Values From January To May 2020

Month	Exchange rate USD/RUB	Brent oil prices (USD)	RTS Index (USD)	Federal loan bonds owned by non-residents (billion RUB)
Jan	61,8121	58,16	1517,07	2 870
Feb	63,9798	51,52	1299,69	3 014
Mar	78,442	23,74	1014,44	3 185
Apr	74,7635	19,23	1125,03	2 892
May	72,5003	36,44	1219,76	2 992
$R^2 = 0.981$				

We will analyze these indicators by multiple regression. The multiple regression equation is obtained:

$$\text{Exchange rate USD/RUB} = -44.2258 - 0.6286\text{Brent oil prices} + 0.03079\text{RTS Index} + 0.03353\text{Federal loan bounds owned by non residents} \quad (2)$$

IV. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Interpretation of multiple regression coefficients. The constant estimates the aggregated effect of other factors on the Exchange rate result and means that in the absence of independent variables would be -44.2258. The coefficient b_1 indicates that with an increase of Brent oil prices by 1, Exchange rate

USD/RUB decreases by 0.6286. The coefficient b_2 indicates that with an increase of RTS Index by 1, Exchange rate USD/RUB increases by 0.03079. The coefficient b_3 indicates that with an increase of Federal loan bonds owned by non-residents by 1, Exchange rate USD/RUB increases by 0.03353.

By conducting an analysis for multicollinearity (dependence between factors) by the Farrar-Glober method, with which the multicollinearity of all factors is tested and separately according to the criteria of Fisher and Student, it was revealed that all factors are multicollinear.

It will be funded the paired correlation coefficients, which shows a consistent change in the two features, reflecting the fact that the variability of one feature is in accordance with the variability of the other.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\bar{x}\bar{y}-\bar{x}\bar{y}}{s(x)\cdot s(y)} \quad (3)$$

where x are the values taken in the sample X , y are the values taken in the sample Y ; \bar{x} is the average value for X , \bar{y} is the average value for Y

$$r_{yx_1} = \frac{2566.611-37.818\cdot 70.3}{15.147\cdot 6.373} = -0.953 \quad (4)$$

The values of the paired correlation coefficient indicate a very strong linear relationship between Brent oil prices and exchange rate of the USD/RUB.

$$r_{yx_2} = \frac{858809.208-1235.198\cdot 70.3}{170.13\cdot 6.373} = -0.945 \quad (5)$$

The coefficient indicates a very strong linear relationship between RTS Index and exchange rate of the USD/RUB.

$$r_{yx_3} = \frac{210642.111-2990.6\cdot 70.3}{111.899\cdot 6.373} = 0.567 \quad (6)$$

The coefficient indicates a moderate linear relationship between Federal loan bonds owned by non-residents and exchange rate of the USD/RUB.

$$r_{x_1x_2} = \frac{49071.601-1235.198\cdot 37.818}{170.13\cdot 15.147} = 0.915 \quad (7)$$

The values of the paired correlation coefficient indicate a very strong linear relationship between Brent oil prices and RTS Index.

$$r_{x_1x_3} = \frac{112490.804-2990.6\cdot 37.818}{111.899\cdot 15.147} = -0.359 \quad (8)$$

The values of the paired correlation coefficient indicate a weak linear relationship between Brent oil prices and Federal loan bonds owned by non-residents.

$$r_{x_2x_3} = \frac{3681071.328-2990.6\cdot 1235.198}{111.899\cdot 170.13} = -0.678 \quad (9)$$

The values of the paired correlation coefficient indicate a moderate linear relationship between RTS Index and Federal loan bonds owned by non-residents.

Calculated paired correlation coefficients that determine the tightness of the relationship between the two features, it was obtained that a change in the exchange rate of the US dollar in Russian rubles leads to a practical similar change in the price of oil BRENT and the RTS index, since the correlation coefficients are greater than 0.9. The average correlation shows the amount of RTS Index and Federal loan bonds owned by non-residents, which is approximately 0.7. A weak relationship, the correlation coefficient value is approximately 0.3, shows the volume of Federal loan bonds owned by non-residents and the price of BRENT oil.

It will be made a system of equations for finding β -coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned} -0.953 &= \beta_1 + 0.915\beta_2 - 0.359\beta_3 \\ -0.945 &= 0.915\beta_1 + \beta_2 - 0.678\beta_3 \\ 0.567 &= -0.359\beta_1 - 0.678\beta_2 + \beta_3 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

This system of linear equations is solved by the Gauss method: $\beta_1 = -1.494$; $\beta_2 = 0.822$; $\beta_3 = 0.589$.

It will be calculated a standardized regression equation, due to which it is possible to evaluate the influence of factors using β -coefficients.

The following standardized equation was obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Exchange rate USD/RUB} &= \\ &= -1.494\text{Brent oil prices} + 0.822\text{RTS Index} + \\ &+ 0.589\text{Federal loan bonds owned by non residents} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Since all standardized β -coefficients are more than 0.5, they have a serious impact on the US dollar exchange rate in Russian rubles, the BRENT oil price has the largest weight of the coefficient.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper discusses the impact of the coronavirus pandemic on the exchange rate of the Russian national currency. Based on the literature review, the study has designed the correlation-regression equation, which shows the relationship and effect of independent variables on the value of the dependent variable.

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded the following conclusions:

Since the beginning of 2020, exchange rate USD/RUB has grown significantly due to the declaration of a pandemic COVID-19 and the introduction of a number of restrictions on the economies of all countries.

The pandemic of coronavirus showed a huge dependence of the ruble exchange rate on the price of oil, which cannot inspire optimism, since this dependence greatly affects the economy of the Russian Federation.

The RTS index is strongly interconnected with indicators such as the ruble exchange rate and the price of oil and, accordingly, can be used both for analysis of the exchange rate and for analysis of the economy of the Russian Federation, as an indicator of the state of large domestic companies.

The volume of federal loan bonds owned by non-residents cannot be considered as an indicator of exchange rate change, but it is an indicator by which the behavior of foreign investors in case of exchange rate change can be judged.

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ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF PLACING KOSOVO-METOHILJA WINE ON THE INTERNATIONAL MARKET

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Abstract

Wine production in Kosovo and Metohija has a long, centuries-old tradition, but unlike some previous times where wine was produced in large economic systems, today wine is produced in small and medium-sized family and local wineries. Small private wineries are becoming the backbone of wine production. Kosovo and Metohija are part of the global market, which in recent years has been trying to become part of the wine quality management system. Wine quality management is achieved by implementing concepts related to the quality of wine systems through the International Organization for Standardization (ISO)¹ and Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP)². So, the concept of wine quality management is integrated from growing grapes in vineyards with the application of modern grape production technology with the application of ISO and HACCP standards in order to offer quality wine to the discerning market. Wineries in Kosovo and Metohija are not only based on the economic profitability of marketing wine to international markets, but also on quality.

Keywords: grapes, wine, wineries, export.

Methodological research

The aim of the work is to indicate the effects of growing vines and wine on an international level, while on a micro level the focus is on the area of Kosovo and Metohija. Several scientific methods were used in the work (method of generalization, comparison and classification, analytical and synthesis method). We obtained the necessary data from domestic professional literature dealing with this topic. Data from temporary institutions from Kosovo and Metohija as well as special publications from this area were used.

INTRODUCTION

The wine-growing region of Kosovo - Metohija includes two sub-regions: northern and southern. The northern subregion includes wines from the Istočki and Peč vineyards. The southern sub-region unites wine production from the Đakovo, Orahorački, Prizren, Suvorečka and Mališevo vineyards, with the largest being

the Orahovačka vineyard. The vineyards are located at an altitude of 300 to 600 meters above sea level, on moderately steep to gentle slopes. Soil types such as loam and alluvial soil, humus-silicate soil and other types of soil prevail.

After 2000, the tradition of viticulture in the north of Kosmet was renewed with large plantations on the slopes of Kopaonik and Rogozna near Leposavić. Given the known political situation in Kosovo and Metohija, the wine industry is regulated by two laws: the Wine Law of the Republic of Serbia, which defines two wine regions (North Metohija and South Metohija) and the Kosovo Wine Law, which was passed by the temporary institutions of Kosovo after the unilateral declaration of independence in 2008. Pristina institutions define two regions (Dukadinski region and Kosovo Plain region). Therefore, Serbs from Kosovo and Metohija harmonized their wine production with

¹ The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) defines a wide range of conditions related to quality management that are applicable to all products. Therefore, the ISO 9000 document defines quality as a preferred characteristic that a product must have, e.g. the product must be reliable, usable and repairable.

² HACCP is a system that can be used as a series of procedures to control processes and sensitive points in the food production chain, with the ultimate goal that the consumer consumes food, in a condition and in a way that will be safe for his health.